

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF NEGATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the linguistic features of negations in English. The features of teaching the pragmatic aspect of negation in English on a linguistic-cognitive basis are considered. The functional side of denial is analyzed as a negative communicative reaction, which plays an important role in the process of verbal communication.

Negation is one of the inherently existing undivided semantically connotational categories characteristic of the entire linguistic picture of the world, which cannot be defined through simpler semantic elements. Negation can be expressed by negative words, a negative prefix, a negative form of a verb, and may also not be expressed separately, that is, as a component of the meaning of a word or an entire sentence.

A classification of negative communicative reactions is given and their distinctive features are mentioned. The possibility of simultaneous teaching of verbal and non-verbal means of conveying negative meanings within the framework of teaching English, built on a linguo-cognitive basis, is substantiated. A number of examples of the successful application of such teaching are given, which are based on gestures and body movements, which act as both a teaching tool and an object of study. The necessity of teaching students the peculiarities of non-verbal communicative behavior of native speakers as an important aspect of the studied linguistic culture is substantiated. Recommendations are given for optimizing the educational process, built on a linguo-cognitive basis for the harmonious integration into it of a number of techniques developed as part of the traditional approach to teaching a foreign language, which demonstrates the integrative nature of such innovative teaching. Some difficulties that may arise when organizing classes on a linguistic-cognitive basis are given, and ways to solve them are proposed.

Each language develops its own system of specific linguistic means, which consolidates the concept of negation, and chooses the leading way of denoting it in different manifestations. Negation can be expressed by linguistic means belonging to different levels of

language. Consequently, it is promising to study the phenomena of negation in different languages using a comparative method, which allows us to determine specific features and at the same time draw some philological and typological conclusions in the aspect of translation.

There are several aspects to the study of denial. In predicate logic, such a concept is formalized using the negation operator, which turns a true proposition into a false one and vice versa. According to the pragmatic concept, negation is not a purely grammatical category, but a complex communicative operation with the help of which the speaker communicates to the addressee his attitude towards a certain fact.

As for grammatical negation, negation is usually understood as a word or affix indicating the absence of an object, qualitative characteristics of an object, actions or states, as well as a linguistic connective - a word-sentence expressing disagreement with the statement. Adjacent to the grammatical understanding of communicative linguistics is a complex pragma linguistic aspect of the study, which draws on data from some psychological works. Denial is considered as a reflection of the negative manifestations of the human psyche in relation to reality and the real situation, enshrined in language. Each language exhibits its own specifics of communication. Since here the peculiarities of national rituals, everyday habits, everything that is accepted and not accepted in everyday behavior are superimposed. What is acceptable or not in the social etiquette of native speakers of English.

According to the analysis, two functions of the impact of negative statements were identified: prescriptive and commentary. Prescriptive statements form a dialogical dominant, characterized by a greater strength of the vector of intention to change the situation. The functional relationships of stereotypical statements are distributed along the scale of expression of categorical or categorical expression of will, i.e.: - prohibitions, orders, appeals, warnings (advice), refutations. The most common group in English are statements expressing refutations. for example: "Is he a friend of yours?" – said Lucy. "Absolutely not" – she said, abruptly. The statement expresses a decisive refutation of what was said with elements of emotional expressiveness, in this case, irritation. The purpose of the orders is to interrupt speech contact, that is, the orders contain a prohibition to continue the conversation. but at the same time closely correlate with calls. Linguistic prohibitions are usually verbless statements that have a secondary predicate structure expressing negation in the sense of a prohibition to say anything, for example: No parking!; No talking!; No smoking! A less common group of negative statements are warnings (advice). Advice is mainly expressed using modal verbs, which convey the speaker's attitude towards the interlocutor. As in the case of the English language, the linguistic units in question are used according to a similar pattern: orders, calls, prohibitions, warnings (advice), refutations. For example, in the meaning of refutation we can find the following statements: not at all; not at all; nothing like this. The meaning of these statements may be implied: - I refute what - you say, or what I said earlier.

As in English, language prohibitions are used to mean the impossibility of doing something: Don't even dream about it!; In no case! The group of warnings includes statements expressing warnings: God forbid!; God forbid! Commentary statements are distinguished on the basis of the operation of preference / or possible denial of a particular phenomenon by

the speaker. Preference can arise either as a reaction to a request or other prescription, or as an unexpected reaction of the speaker to elements of a speech situation. The main means of expressing negation is the negative component no/not. Commentary is represented by statements, words or phrases of disagreement, objection, refusal. The most common among negative statements are disagreements, which are characterized by, for example: "You're going to remind my debt, aren't you?" "Not on your life!" Such an expressive verbless statement expresses categorical disagreement using the negative component "Not" and, in addition, using the stylistic device of hyperbole. Objections usually include emotionally charged statements associated with the speaker's irritation, for example, a statement like "Now, what are you going to put on for your Birthday?" "This" – I muttered sulkily. "Oh, don't be silly, you can't wear that on your Birthday." Such statements emphasize the impossibility of performing any action. In this case, the speaker seeks to humiliate the interlocutor; the interactional essence of the utterance lies in the objection. The group of linguistic refusals includes utterances that involve strengthening communicative intent. Basically, such statements are based on a negative component, but in this group you can also find statements such as, for example: "Do you want a biscuit?" "No, thank you" - expressing a polite refusal of an offer made by the interlocutor. In the Russian language, the most frequently used statements are those that can be considered refusals and disagreements. For example, by using communicative words without a negative nomination: Nonsense!; No way! In general, such utterances do not contain a negative linguistic operator or speaker. Such statements and words express a negative meaning towards the speaker. This looks like making a negative assessment of the interlocutor's words. However, over time, these statements lose their linguistic value and retain only the function of categorical linguistic negation. Verbal statement: Have mercy! Don't tell (you)! represent disagreement. Analysis of literary texts showed that linguistic negation is used in two functions of influence: prescriptive and commentary. In literary texts, negation is used in various functional semantic meanings and can act as an order, call, warning (advice), refutation, disagreement, objection, refusal.

An important aspect of comprehensive teaching of a foreign language in general and negation in English in particular is taking into account the nonverbal aspect of communication and the characteristics of the means of its expression. The advantage of the linguocognitive approach here is the fact that teaching negation is based on the principles of maximum use of the target language in the classroom, and new material, including grammatical material, for the explanation of which previously it was necessary to resort to the students' native language, can now be conveyed using other means, primarily non-verbal [4; 5].

Based on the role assigned to students in the structure of tasks, R. Holm identifies means focused on active and passive perception of the material. The author classifies as passively oriented a wide range of schematic images, diagrams, and concept maps that explain the nature of the phenomenon under study in its connection with the corresponding conceptual structures and mechanisms. On the contrary, actively oriented means imply the direct participation of students in the process of generating, visualizing, modifying and interpreting meanings. Such means include movements, gestures, facial expressions, the involvement of which solves the problem of not only better involvement of students in the educational

process, since students themselves embody the meanings under consideration, but also their awareness of non-verbal communication in the linguistic culture being studied [6].

Unlike the traditional approach, in which teaching students the peculiarities of gestures, facial expressions, and movements that have a certain meaning in a situation of communication with a native speaker requires additional time in class or the organization of a special course, in the structure of a lesson built on a linguocognitive basis, such training takes place of course, since it is both a teaching method and its subject. Thus, the methodology of teaching grammar by J.-M. Lapere is based on the principle that linguistic phenomena, in particular grammatical ones, can be visualized and perceived through body language. This method fully meets the student-centric nature of foreign language classes, since students use movements and gestures to embody both grammatical and mental structures. In addition, this organization of lessons makes it possible to make learning interactive and maintain student motivation at a high level. By perceiving the material not so much as abstract information, but as a sensory, tangible experience, students can better understand and assimilate it [4]. Speaking about the use of body language when teaching a foreign language, R. Holm notes that in contrast to the “virtual embodiment” of the phenomena under consideration, to which he includes diagrams, diagrams, drawings and images, “kinesthetic embodiment” opens up the possibility of direct interaction with the structure being studied, be it linguistic or mental [6]. In other words, students here are not just passive observers and receptors of information, but, on the contrary, can embody the phenomena under consideration and even change them through their own participation in them. Simpler situations, for example, the expression of such an aspect of denial as prohibition, which requires two participants for such a kinesthetic representation, can be modified by involving a third student, spreading his arms to the sides to express the additional meaning of regret about the prohibition, which demonstrates the accessibility and flexibility of this technique [3; 6]. The promise of using such a linguocognitive approach to teaching students grammar in English was demonstrated by M. Giovanelli [5]. Instead of explaining the material in the students’ native language, he proposed a number of ways to visualize various linguistic phenomena, and the meanings and cognitive mechanisms behind them through movements, facial expressions, and gestures. According to the researcher, this method of presenting material, in addition to increasing the level of student involvement in the educational process, is in good agreement with the communicative orientation of foreign language teaching, promotes student work in groups and the overall student-centeredness of classes. Among other things, this approach to teaching allows students to develop a better understanding of the very essence of the phenomena under consideration in their inextricable connection with the mental processes of the speakers of the linguistic culture being studied, which gave rise to the corresponding meanings that are embodied in linguistic phenomena, in particular grammatical ones [4; 6]. Thanks to this structure of the lesson, students, visualizing the necessary meanings through sign language and movements accepted in the country of the language being studied, “get used to” the role of a native speaker, while simultaneously mastering the features of non-verbal communication in the linguistic culture in question.

To illustrate the above, let us turn to the features of teaching negation, built on a linguocognitive foundation, and, in particular, such an aspect as the negative communicative reaction of prohibition. As noted above, such training can be built on the basis of visualizing the meaning of a statement through movements, body position, facial expressions: – You can't go there: the first student strives to go forward, while the second holds the partner's hand and does not allow him to perform the action; – I'm really sorry, but you can't go there: the second student, holding the hand of the first, bows before him, thus, in addition to the actual negative meaning, expressing the additional meaning of the statement - regret about the ban; – I'm not sure that you can go there: the first student heads forward, while the second one spreads his arms, demonstrating uncertainty about the correctness of such a decision; – You are not allowed here: while the first student is trying to enter the classroom, the second one is holding the door, preventing them from going inside; – You can't sit down here: the first student's attempt to sit down at the table is interrupted by the second, who, sitting at the table, puts out his hand with the palm facing him, similarly prohibiting the action [3]. The given examples illustrate a number of advantages of this method of teaching a foreign language. Information is presented in the most accessible and visual form without using the students' native language for explanation. The language of movement and gestures used promotes maximum student engagement by complementing instructions in the target language, which, in isolation from such visual representation, may not be fully understandable to students. Thus, the level of interference between conceptual structures associated with the learner's native language and those related to the target language is reduced. This allows us to talk about a step towards approaching the level of a native speaker in mastering the corresponding linguistic culture, since such a level does not imply a mechanical ordering of linguistic units based on the mental structures and cultural code of the native language, which can lead to distortions, inaccuracies, errors, but primarily the formation the student has a conceptual system similar to that of a native speaker. Such a system includes the specifics of the use of linguistic and extralinguistic means of expressing meanings, and the cultural component, and, ultimately, the features of the conceptualization of reality inherent in the society of interest to us. Thus, the student can look at the surrounding reality from the perspective of the linguistic culture being studied, which is expressed both in an increase in the level of language mastery and in a better understanding of the peculiarities of thinking and worldview of its speakers, which is important within the framework of the dialogue of cultures. Thus, the training of students, built on a similar principle, meets the requirements of comprehensive and harmonious education, affecting the linguistic, extralinguistic, cultural components of education in their inextricable connection with the conceptual picture of the world of the bearer of English linguistic culture.

Thus, a negative reaction at the nominative and communicative level is always "contamination." Each specified type has a special communicative goal, certain concepts of the speaker and interlocutor. It contains event content, the factor of linguo communicative past and future. Depending on the reason for the occurrence of acts of prohibition, refusal, disagreement, the speaker chooses lexical and grammatical means of expression and takes certain communicative steps.

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